

Reimagining Schliemann's Troy by Brian Paul Kaess

"Is this the face that launched a thousand ships that burnt the topless towers of Ilium?... Oh sweet Helen, make me immortal with thy kiss, thou art fairer than the evening air clad in a beauty of a thousand stars."¹ - Marlowe, Christopher. *Doctor Faustus*. Scene 12.

It is true that Heinrich Schliemann¹ was not the 1st to 'test the Homeric Question with the spade²,¹ but perhaps what was more interesting is, he was not the last to intrepert which layer of Troy was the actual location of Priam's Gate, or what one might call Bronze Age Troy. By the second half of the nineteenth century, two principal sites had been associated with Homeric Troy: Pinarbasi-Balli Dag and Hisarlik³. His friend Frank Calvert had suggested he dig at Hisarlik, even though the site at the time believed to be Homer's Troy was nearby Pinarbasi. Previous excavations had suggested that there was no preclassical occupation there, even though the guidebooks told Schliemann Pinarbasi was Troy. So this was a disappointment⁴. Perhaps that is why at Frank Calvert's nudging, an English man who worked as the American Consul to the Dardenelles and a local authority on Trojan topography, he began digging at Hisarlik, what many now believe to be the location of Bronze Age Troy, the Troy of Helen and Achilles and many of the *Illiad's* heroes. Visitors to the area made frequent use of Calvert's knowledge of the Troad, who had become a local expert of sorts, performing valuable excavations of his own. Engineer Franz Kauffer was the first to map Hisarlik in 1787. Calvert had even dug trenches into the hill on the eastern side of Hisarlik, but he did not have sufficient funds to continue on a grand scale. What Calvert had started, Schliemann would finish. Calvert sensed that Schliemann was the tool he could use to make the breakthrough he suspected was always there. Calvert didn't seem to care who took the credit. Art for art's sake, so to speak.

So, indeed, it was Frank Calvert who had suggested to Schliemann that Hisarlik with Troy, but it was finally Heinrich Schliemann who had excavated it on a grand scale. Together, Schliemann and Calvert would go on to settle the 'Homeric Question.'¹ Schliemann had to practically jump through hoops to get permits to dig, as the local authorities did not want him to own the land found in the *Illiad*. But this did not deter him. With the aid of John P. Brown, diplomatic agent for the United States in Istanbul, Schliemann received the permission to fulfill his dream of uncovering Homeric Troy. Schliemann's interest began gradually, and then increased steadily, becoming more detailed as he made progress and then, culminated in one of the most remarkable discoveries by an amateur archaeologist ever recorded: the discovery that Hisarlik was indeed the ancient city of Troy. His claim, in May 1873, to have uncovered 'Priam's

¹ See Heinrich Schliemann *Britannica.com*

² See 'Heinrich Schliemann: Hero or Fraud?' D.F. Easton May-June 1988 *The Classical World* p. 339.

³ See Chapter 'The Discovery of Troy: Schliemann and the Ottomans in the 1870s' in *Homer, Troy and the Turks*, 2017, p. 38.

⁴ See 'Heinrich Schliemann: Hero or Fraud?' D.F. Easton May-June 1988 *The Classical World* p. 339.

Treasure⁵ was hailed around the world. Schliemann became world-famous as the excavator of Troy.

As one historian notes: 'The desire to confirm the historical reality of the Trojan War and to prove the existence of Homer's locations and heroes preoccupied many minds.' It had become a European craze of sorts. Schliemann had started as a mere grocer and now wanted to finish as a scholar and intellectual. He had traveled the world and now settled down in Paris to study archeology and such. His amassed wealth allowed him to indulge in any of his hobbies, and having sensed this, he jumped into archeology with a passion. He wanted to settle the question of 'ubi Troia fuit' or 'where Troy was.' There is an old saying, 'From small things come great things' and Schliemann was a perfect example of this.

Many try to reconcile the fact that Schliemann's foreman Yannakis basically identified only bronze items in the collection of 'Priam's Treasure' when it was supposedly found. That if the foreman Yannakis had seen only these bronze items, then how do we later account for silver and gold items found and considered as an integral part of the collection? I offer a 'divided treasure' theory as to why some claim only bronze items were initially found in 'Priam's Treasure'. I offer that Schliemann surreptitiously created two portions of treasure, on the very day of discovery- a 'weak' portion composed of bronze items intended for govt. inspection and a 'strong' portion composed of silver and gold items which he wished to keep for himself. Eventually he whisked both 'portions' out of the Ottoman Empire through his usual guile.

The Government Representative, Amin Efendi, had already been alerted by the workmen at Hisarlik that there was a valuable find⁶. Maybe Afendi had told the workmen to be on the lookout ahead of time and Schliemann had gotten wind of this. So then Schliemann, on the day of discovery, had prepared the bronze items (on that very day of discovery) in a separate collection than the rest in case he had to show it to Efendi. Perhaps Schliemann had made an arrangement with the workers to give him so much time, before they alerted Efendi, so he could cover his tracks, by dividing the treasure, a 'strong' one for himself, and a 'weaker' one for possible show to the govt. By the time the govt. got wind of this, he would have the most valuable part of the treasure whisked out of the country. No doubt he wanted to keep the silver and gold items for himself, under this scenario. Perhaps he went so far as to deceive his foreman Yannakis as well, in case the Representative interrogated him too. In this case, no one is being deceptive except the usual suspect: Schliemann. On the other hand, Yannakis could well have been in on the game, since it is he and another man, Spiridon Demetriou, who went by night six days later to Thymbra Farm to collect the Treasure.

As D.F. Easton notes⁷: "We now hear not of six baskets and a bag but of six crates and a bag, so presumably they re-packed it. From the Calverts they borrowed three horses, setting two crates on each horse, and, through the dark, made their way North across the Trojan Plain to a quiet beach, Karanlik Limani. Here at a rendezvous probably arranged by

⁵ *Ibid.* p. 341.

⁶ See 'Priam's Gold: the Full Story' D. F. *Easton Anatolian Studies*, Vol. 44 (1994), p. 222.

⁷ *Ibid.* p. 225.

the Greek Consul, a Greek Ship, the Taxiarches, was waiting- a ship Schliemann had used for such purposes before.... and the ship set sail for the island of Syros."

In the end, when Efendi arrived and demanded to see the treasure, Schliemann himself refused, perhaps never intending to share a 'juicy' find at the site with the Ottoman Govt.⁸ Under my theory, Schliemann kept both the 'weaker' or bronze part of the treasure as well as the stronger or 'silver and gold' part of the treasure for himself. It was as if Schliemann had prepared two knapsacks and, in the end, kept them both. He never handed over anything of 'Priam's Treasure' but whisked it out of the country as if previously arranged. If Schliemann's motives here are not pure, it is no surprise. This was quintessential Schliemann: scholar and thief.

Under this scenario, the bronze, silver & gold items of the collection were all initially found together, but were immediately divided surreptitiously so Schliemann would have a greater chance of keeping the more valuable portion. Yannakis, Spiridon Demetriou, & the Calverts could have all easily been in on the game from the start, but one thing is for sure, they were all in at the end and an integral part of Schliemann's heist of the Treasure back to Greece six days later. In conclusion, I argue they were merely part and parcel of Schliemann's well-oiled machine and not the least bit above fraud and chicanery- from start to finish.

By 1882, he was joined by an able, young architect named Wilhelm Dörpfeld⁹, who some called his greatest discovery, and it was perhaps this infusion of young talent that helped sharpen up Schliemann's own skills, as we can see in the improvement of his note-taking. His digging methods were initially crude, but his strategy was not stupid. He was perfectly able to distinguish Early Bronze Age architecture from Late Bronze Age or Roman. Stratigraphy was one of his strong points, and he had been alerted to this by his friend Frank Calvert, who had an interest in Geology. Yet which strata was the actual Troy would turn out to hinge on a process of trial-and-error akin to some case study in scientific method. Dörpfeld corrected Schliemann, only to discover what he had corrected might be more accurate than his own proposal. Had Schliemann been right after all? Let us observe and see for ourselves.

With blood, sweat and tears, Schliemann and his team were able to distinguish first five, then seven, and then finally nine layers that represented different periods of the site. But what he was really after was Priam's Troy, whose layer he documented the most of any of the other strata. So in time he became an expert. Schliemann really wanted to know if he had encountered the Homeric Troy of old, and he certainly began to believe that Hisarlik was Troy, that he was walking in the foot steps of those ancient Greek heroes. But his own interpretation he took to be fact and as one writer states: 'It is a recurrent problem in Schliemann. The burnt citadel of Troy II was Troy; the gate was the Scaean Gate; the building inside the gate was Priam's palace, and the treasure was Priam's Treasure¹⁰.' In 1882, Dörpfeld suggested to Schliemann that the multiple burnt strata of Troy II-III might be the Priam's Troy that Schliemann was looking for but that was shelved

⁸ *Ibid.* p. 222.

⁹ Wilhelm Dörpfeld *Wikipedia.org*.

¹⁰ See 'Heinrich Schliemann: Hero or Fraud?' D.F. Easton May-June 1988 *The Classical World* p. 341.

later. However, stronger interpretations of the strata emerged. The pottery of Troy II didn't fit and this became clearer with the discovery of Mycenaean pottery in Troy VI in 1890.

So, Schliemann believed Troy II to be Mycenaean Troy based on material evidence, and Dörpfeld followed with a similar argument for Troy VI and Blegen in favor of Troy VIIa. Hisarlik was believed to be Classical Ilium, a city that was known to exist at the end of the dark ages, which many ancient Greeks believed to be a successor to Troy. This was attested to by Edward Daniel Clarke in 1801 on the basis of coins and inscriptions. But what was lacking is any inscriptions for Troy itself. So when Schliemann said that he discovered Troy, what he really meant was that he proved the historicity of the Trojan War, although Easton disputes this. His rollout of the 'Treasure of Priam' on May 31, 1873¹¹, was undeniably a wakeup call to the archaeological establishment back in Berlin, although there is controversy about what it originally contained and what may have been added. Priam's Treasure¹² was composed of a large, spectacular cache of gold & silver jewelry, bronze bowls and cups, copper axes and other valuables, although some later claimed that the find initially held only bronze items. His entry about it in his diary appears rather sketchy. This was one of the so-called hoaxes Schliemann was known for and detracted from his later fame although initially he basked in the lustre of discovery.

Yet, Schliemann could be touching as well to the public, not just a bulldozer of fraud. This was evidenced in the image found in his Wikipedia article of Sophia Schliemann¹³ wearing precious finds recovered at Hisarlik.

Now let us look at Frank Calvert's influence upon Schliemann and his work. Frank Calvert, in 1857, believed that Hanay Tepe was the communal burial spot of the Trojans. His brother Frederick Calvert had thought Thymbra Farm was the site of Hellenic Troy, but Frank disagreed¹⁴. Using Strabo as his guide, Calvert identified the sites of Larisa and Coloniae¹⁵. Calvert noted Newton's earlier skepticism about the suitability of Pinarbasi as the site of ancient Troy. He later noted the stones at Pinarbasi were smaller than they should have been for Mycenaean cities, such as Mycenae, Larisa (at Argos), and Tiryns¹⁶. Based on pottery styles, he thought Pinarbasi might be Gergis. With an idea of Hisarlik's potential noted from Newton as well as the armchair identification of Troy with Hisarlik from McClaren, Calvert thereafter purchased acreage there and the highest mound or acropolis in 1864 or 1865. The stage was being set.

The British Museum refused to pay for his dig and perhaps this is where Schliemann stepped in to fill the vacuum¹⁷. By the time Schliemann arrived, Calvert had already dug trenches 12-15 feet deep. They met on August 15, 1868, and Calvert must have seized on

¹¹ *Ibid.* p. 336.

¹² See Chapter 'The Discovery of Troy: Schliemann and the Ottomans in the 1870s' in *Homer, Troy and the Turks*, 2017, p. 35.

¹³ Heinrich Schliemann *Wikipedia.org*

¹⁴ See "Finding the Walls of Troy": Frank Calvert, Excavator. Susan Hueck Allen, Jul 1995 *American Journal of Archeology* p. 387.

¹⁵ *Ibid.* p. 387.

¹⁶ *Ibid.* p. 390.

¹⁷ *Ibid.* p. 392.

the chance to convince Schliemann to commit the resources for a major excavation that he so desperately desired. Schliemann had become his tool to carry out what had been his personal ambition. They both agreed that the Homeric Troad was nowhere else but at Hisarlik.

Once back in Paris, Schliemann corresponded with Calvert, bombarding him with questions, the latter providing answers that would have taken Schliemann years to amass. The wheels were starting to roll. Calvert was willing to give him all the help he needed in carrying on the excavations at Ilium Novum. Schliemann began to realize that Troy was not merely a Homeric myth, but that it was there to be 'dug up.' By December 1868 to February 1869, Schliemann and Calvert were coming to terms and the dig was on. This is evident in their correspondence. Schliemann began digging in 1871 and was in earnest by 1872. Schliemann says, 'I shall take away the whole hill.' Calvert advised Schliemann on dating the strata by using the pottery styles that were found. There was a cooling of the partnership as Schliemann incorrectly dated early material to Homeric times. And it was Schliemann who had smuggled out 'a little broken pottery' ('Priam's Treasure'). Perhaps Schliemann appropriated Calvert's lifelong dream of 'finding the walls of Troy' and converted it for his own use.

Troy VI and VII were not to be discovered until 1890. The stirrup jars that Schliemann discovered in Troy VI were long-sought-after proof of the site being contemporaneous with other Homeric sites such as Mycenaean or Tiryns. It is perhaps fitting that Schliemann had lived to see that day. Until then Calvert had been skeptical that Schliemann had unearthed anything of the Homeric Age. Hanay Tepe was now ruled out as the home of the Trojans. The Walls of Troy were identified three years after Schliemann's death, by his assistant Wilhelm Dörpfeld. Calvert also stated that Hisarlik may have been a ruin when Homer wrote. Calvert concluded: 'For if ever the world-famed city existed (Homeric Troy), the probability is that Hisarlik marks its site.'

There is now general agreement that Dörpfeld's identification of Troy VIh with the city of Priam is correct¹⁸, as long as Hisarlik is to be identified with Troy and there was in fact a Trojan War. Troy looks like it could have contained at most, 6,000 inhabitants, at its height. The bulk of the population must have lived outside. It was likely a walled city and its main feature was its fortified acropolis. It is even possible that the Trojan horse, featured in the *Iliad*, was a metaphor for an ancient siege tower. Trevor R. Bryce believes the Trojan War may have been fought at about 1250 BCE and this also concurs with Herodotus' *Histories*¹⁹. Traditionalists believe the Fall of Troy occurred on April 24, 1184 BCE²⁰. Blegen argued that Troy VIIa was Homer's Troy, but ceramic evidence later refuted this. Moreover, Troy was likely a vassal state of the Hittite Empire, but it may also be true that the Trojans and Greeks were somehow ethnically related as distant cousins.

¹⁸ See 'The Trojan War: is there Truth behind the Legend?' Trevor R. Bryce *Near Eastern Archaeology*, Vol. 65, No. 3 (Sep., 2002), p. 186.

¹⁹ *ibid.* p. 186.

²⁰ See *History & Headlines: April 24, 1184 B.C.: The Fall of Troy*
<https://www.historyandheadlines.com/april-24-1184-b-c-fall-troy/>

Despite the paucity of written evidence at Hisarlik, there is one valuable piece that posterity has been left at the site. That is a biconvex bronze seal (bearing a brief inscription in Luwian hieroglyphs) found in a house in stratum VIIb²¹. This may provide a clue to the ethnicity of the inhabitants of Troy. One side gives the name of a man, whose profession is scribe, and the other side has a name of a woman, presumably his wife. Luwians lived in western Anatolia at this time and some believe that Wilusa was the Hittite name for Troy/Ilios. Wilusa is mentioned in Hittite letters as having been attacked. Could this have been Troy?

One of the letters attributed to the Hittite King Ahhiyawa, the so-called Tawagalawa Letter²², regarding a war with Wilusa, dates to the middle of the thirteenth century, which is also the most widely accepted time frame for the destruction of Troy VIIh. So the secret to understanding the Trojans might not just be Luwian records or script, but Hittite as well.

Schliemann certainly was no paragon of virtue or honesty. For instance, later scholars debunked the 'Dream of Troy'²³ of his youth, and said he even lied about certain meetings with politicians merely to raise his fame. This has become the *topoi* or common-place view of Schliemann, that he was a pathological liar²⁴ or told less than the unvarnished truth. There is little doubt Schliemann had a businessman's insistence on his own greatness and never wanted to deviate from this narrative. He liked to portray himself in a favorable light²⁵. Yet, one gets the feeling he must have felt he was 'hot on the trail' of something magnificent, the discovery of an ancient city, and he felt so strongly about it that he poured his treasure into it and made it his life's work. Schliemann believed.

But one must also add a disclaimer here that if it was Schliemann who believed, then certainly it was Calvert and others who pointed the way. Schliemann could be a 'Rhino of energy' once he had his heart set, and so, in a sense, needed careful prodding. This is what Calvert provided.

Some of us would never deign to breach the fortress of Schliemann admirers, and he still figures as a heroic portrait to many, including myself. Let us hope this admiration continues unabated. With Schliemann, we practically hear the muster roll of the ships of the *Illiad* being called out. To call Schliemann a fraud would be like questioning the veracity of the celebrated Mask of Agememnon²⁶, which Schliemann uncovered at

²¹ See 'The Trojan War: is there Truth behind the Legend?' Trevor R. Bryce *Near Eastern Archaeology*, Vol. 65, No. 3 (Sep., 2002), p. 189.

²² *Ibid.* p. 192.

²³ See 'An Archeologist on the Schliemann Controversy' by Wolfgang Schindler Spring 1992 *Illinois Classical Studies* p. 137.

²⁴ *Ibid.* p. 137.

²⁵ See 'Heinrich Schliemann: Hero or Fraud?' D.F. Easton May-June 1988 *The Classical World* p. 338.

²⁶ See The "Face of Agamemnon" Oliver Dickinson in *Hesperia: The Journal of the American School of Classical Studies at Athens*, Vol. 74, No. 3 (Jul. - Sep., 2005), pp. 299-308.

Mycenae in 1876. It may be a fraud, but it was an interesting one at that and might just as well turn out to be true.